

PRIORITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND PHYSICAL CULTURE

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Abstract: much attention is paid to the reforms carried out in our country, the protection and strengthening of the health of the younger generation, the provision of health-improving programs in education in all parts of the educational process. Therefore, the foundations of physical education and sports are laid in educational issues, mainly from childhood and adolescence.

This article examines the priorities of the development of physical education and Physical Culture.

Keywords: physical education, physical culture, sports, adolescence, mass sports.

ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ

Аннотация: большое внимание уделяется реформам, проводимым в нашей стране, защите и укреплению здоровья подрастающего поколения, обеспечению оздоровительных программ во всех сферах образовательного процесса. Поэтому основы физической культуры и спорта закладываются в образовательных учреждениях преимущественно с детства и юности.

В данной статье рассмотрены приоритетные направления развития физической культуры и физической культуры.

Ключевые слова: физкультура, физическая культура, спорт, подростковый возраст, массовый спорт.

JISMONIY TARBIYA VA JISMONIY MADANIYAT TARAQQIYOTINING USTIVOR YO'NALISHLARI

Annotatsiya: mamlakatimizda olib borilayotgan islohotlar, yosh avlod salomatligini sog'lomlashtirish dasturlarni ta'minlab borilishiga katta e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Shu bois, ta'lim muassasalarida asosan bolalik va o'smirlilik davridan jismoniy tarbiya va sportga poydevor qo'yilgan.

niyat taraqqiyotining ustivor yo'nalishlari tadqiqi etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy tarbiya, jismoniy madaniyat, sport, o'smirlilik davri, ommaviy sport.

INTRODUCTION

During the years of independence of our country, conditions corresponding to modern requirements were created for regular physical education and mass sports of the population, especially the younger generation, in particular students, through sports competitions, strengthening youth confidence in their will, strength and capabilities, fostering a sense of courage and patriotism, devotion to the Motherland, selection of talented athletes. fruitful work was carried out on the systematic organization of acceptance and targeted preparatory work.

At the same time, today the coverage of physical culture and mass sports of all segments of the population, active promotion in all regions of our country of the importance of physical culture and mass sports in the life of a person and family, its one of the main conditions for physical

and spiritual health and maturity, creation of the necessary conditions for young people to realize their abilities and talents, creation, selection of these, the owners of special talents in the field of sports and the improvement of the targeted training system are waiting for solutions on a systematic basis.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

As you know, in the fourth priority direction of the Action Strategy “development of the № PD-3031 “on measures for the further development of physical culture and mass sports”, it was noted that “in all regions of our country, work is being carried out to promote the importance of

The health and educational tasks of physical education are:

- you will be in a good mood all day;
- your work will be productive, and your creative activity will be strong;
- the nervous system is balanced, you become assertive, thoughtful;
- activity, initiative, courage, and a sense of friendship are formed;
- regular physical exercises lead to the formation of hygiene skills;
- the fat layer decreases, you become more compact, more mobile, more agile;
- your muscles will be tightened, and your figure will become beautiful and beautiful;
- improves blood flow in the veins, improves the supply of oxygen and nutrients to the body and organs.;
- increases the protective ability of the body;
- you will be younger, more beautiful, harder working and healthier than others.

“Physical culture is a complex of special events that the builders of a new society, along with the means of physical education in the comprehensive education of mature individuals, assume the physical improvement of a person by specifically targeting him with special means and techniques of sports and culture. Physical culture is a part of the general culture, the development of which depends on the level of socio-economic development of society [2, 57].”

More precisely, physical culture is a part of the general culture, the development of which depends on the level of socio-economic development of society. Physical progress is a natural process associated with the growth of the human body, changing its shape and duration. Physical progress obeys objective biological laws. The main of these laws is the law of unity of the development of the organism and the environment.

The level of development of physical culture in society is assessed by the following indicators:

- according to the degree of introduction of physical culture into the daily life of members of society;
- with the health and physical fitness of community members;
- material and technical support of physical education classes with the provision and their quality;
- the constancy of employees who manage physical education with the composition (staff), qualifications, activity and talent;
- it is evaluated according to the sports results of the members of the society [3, 17].”

In our country, the process of radical renewal and development of all industries is actively carried out, during which great importance is attached to the science of physical culture and sports.

It is no coincidence that the resolutions of our Government emphasize that the wider dissemination of physical culture and sports among the general population is a national matter, the responsibility of professional and academic preschool educational institutions and labor collectives in all places.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the most important basic resources of the physical culture system is sports training. The processes of selecting gifted youth, conducting their tests and experiments and directly engaging in sports are an extremely complex, wide-ranging and multifaceted socio-psychological and psychological process that requires high training. Basically, this implies the following theoretical and practical processes:

- Physical training (general and special physical training);
- Technical and tactical training;
- Spiritual and volitional training;
- Theoretical training.

It should be noted that the above-mentioned areas of sports training are based on training tools, goals and objectives, methods, principles and much more. Because they include their specially directed activities.

Physical training processes consist of two types, namely general development and special physical training, depending on the content, form and goals. Pedagogical processes that have these socio-educational features are not aimed solely at preparing athletes for the Olympic Games. It is possible that the training of pupils in labor and defensive work, when performing certain active actions that occur in everyday life, also has its own needs for physical training.

General physical fitness refers to the physical perfection of each practitioner. That is, to be able to move quickly, easily perform various physical labor, have dexterity, strength and other physical qualities. And in order to possess such qualities and physical qualities, you always need to engage in physical culture and sports. At the same time, it is necessary to include physical education and sports in the daily routine. For this reason, it is necessary to additionally engage in gymnastic exercises in the morning and free time, means of recreational physical culture, and most importantly-to actively participate in all classes of sports clubs organized during the week (from 2-3 times for 1, 5-2 hours).

The main principles of the state policy in the field of physical culture and sports are:

- humanism;
- democracy;
- continuity and duration of physical education of citizens;
- harmonization of state and public administration in the system of physical culture and sports[4].

The formation of a healthy person through physical education, physical culture and sports should become the task of the whole society. Society's respect for continuous physical education and sports leads to the fact that every person, family, parent puts physical education and sports at the level of habit. "In a word, sport remains the most important tool for educating a harmoniously developed generation in our country, and this will inevitably continue in the future. Because sport means a healthy generation, a healthy future. Therefore, only a healthy people, a healthy nation are capable of great things".

It is well known that in our country special attention is paid to the wide promotion of a healthy lifestyle among the younger generation, popularization and development of the sphere of physical culture and sports. As a result of large-scale reforms aimed at achieving a noble goal - to

ensure that today's youth, representatives of the younger generation, who are considered the direct owners of tomorrow, are physically healthy, have a strong will, and also have education and upbringing to grow them into mature people, to educate a generation that has no equal in the world, sports are becoming deeper it penetrates into the lives of our youth, thousands of boys and girls make sports their daily task.

Maintaining a healthy lifestyle and sports has a positive impact on their physical condition and health. It should be noted that it is the development of children's sports in our republic that is given special attention by the head of state and the government, in connection with which large-scale work is being carried out to ensure the implementation of laws, decrees and resolutions.

The model of teacher-coach training in physical culture and sports is determined by state educational standards and standard program requirements for the direction of education in accordance with the law "On Education", "national training program".

CONCLUSION

In any social society, the upbringing of the younger generation is organized with a specific purpose. The purpose of education is determined by the development of social society, the direction of its development, the content of social relations. The main purpose of education, which is being organized in the Republic of Uzbekistan today, is the education and upbringing of a perfect personality. Therefore, it is useful for every person to lead a healthy lifestyle, increase physical activity even more and start these actions today in order to stay healthy and harmonious. And this will inevitably become the spiritual heritage of not only today's, but also tomorrow's generations, will give our people incomparable spiritual strength and wisdom, measurable by nothing.

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